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In-Vitro Efficacy of Crude Botanical Extracts and A Synthetic Insecticide (Imidacloprid) In the Control of Termites; *Macrotermes Spp* (Isoptera: Termitidae) In Kyambogo University, Uganda

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Abstract

Termites especially Macrotermes spp are highly destructive polyphagous insect pests of crop plants (Sseremba et al., 2011). They damage seedlings, wood, fiber and other household cellulose based materials hence a menace to especially to the agricultural sector. To control these damaging and yield-limiting pests, various synthetic insecticides such as Imidacloprid have been recommended and extensively used (UNEP. 2000; Venkateswara et al., 2005). Unfortunately, such insecticides are costly, not environmentally friendly, non-biodegradable and not readily available to especially the rural communities. Furthermore, they are very toxic to even non-target organisms in the ecosystems especially when applied in concentration levels higher than the manufacturers' rates (Dennis, 1981; Pimental, 1995). In the bid to find alternative cheap; readily available; biodegradable and less toxic insecticides, some plant species such as Jatropha curcas, Capsicum spp and Azadirachta indica were discovered to contain insecticidal properties (Ssemaganda et al., 2011). However, in Uganda, very few people especially those in rural areas use these botanical extracts in the control of termites (Ssemaganda et al., 2011). This could mainly be due to the fact that no studies have been carried out to provide relevant and up-to-date information about their efficacy in the control of Macrotermes spp of termites. Therefore, the aim of this study was to assess the efficacy of crude botanical extracts from Jatropha curcas, Capsicum spp and Azadirachta indica and a synthetic insecticide (imidacloprid) in the control of termites. In this study, Jatropha curcas seeds, Capsicum spp ripe fruits and Azadirachta indica leaves were used to obtain the crude extracts whose efficacy against Macrotermes spp was assessed. The used botanical plant materials and termites were collected from Nakasajja Village, Mukono District and the bushes around Kyambogo University, Kampala District using purposive sampling. They were later transported to the Biology Laboratory at the Department of Biological Sciences of Kyambogo University for bioassays. Each crude botanical extract was tested on Macrotermes spp at four (4) concentration levels 5%, 10%, 20% and 30% w/v. Imidacloprid was bought from an Agricultural shop in Kampala, Uganda. It was also tested on Macrotermes spp at four concentration levels 5%, 10%, 20% and 30% (V/v). Distilled water was used as the control for comparison. The design of the study was basically a completely randomized experimental design involving three replicates for each treatment concentration level. All the concentration levels of the botanical extracts were able to cause mortality of Macrotermes spp especially 20% and 30% of Jatropha curcas and Capsicum spp that caused the greatest mortality (100%). The synthetic insecticide (imidacloprid) also caused mortality of Macrotermes spp at all used concentration levels. However 10%, 20% and 30% caused the greatest mortality (100%). At p= 5%, F= 0.989858 and Fcrit = 3.490295. The study demonstrated that all the three used crude botanical extracts possess termiticidal activity especially Jatropha curcas and Capsicum spp which caused 100% mortality at 20% and 30% concentration levels. The synthetic insecticide (Imidacloprid) also caused mortality of Macrotermes spp especially at 10%, 20% and 30% where the mortality was 100%. At p= 5%, F= 0.989858 and Fcrit = 3.490295 hence there was no significant difference in the in-vitro efficacy of the botanical extracts and imidacloprid in controlling termites.

Key words: *Macrotermes spp, Jatropha curcas, Capsicum spp, Azadirachta indica, Imidacloprid*

1- Introduction

Termites especially *Macrotermes spp* are highly destructive polyphagous insect pests of crop plants. They damage seedlings, wood, fiber and other household cellulose based materials hence a menace to especially to the agricultural sector (Sseremba *et al.*, 2011). In the bid to control them, many Ugandan farmers have used various methods such as cultural, mechanical, physical and chemical methods. However, about 80% of the Ugandan population rely on the chemical method which encompasses the use of synthetic insecticides such as imidacloprid, chlorodane and cypermethrin (Sileshi *et al.*, 2010). Unfortunately, most of these insecticides have serious deleterious impacts on non-targeted biotic and abiotic factors of the environment (UNEP. 2000; Venkateswara *et al.*, 2005; Ahmed and Girma, 2013; Koul, 2007). Imidacloprid at a rate of 5% is one of the insecticides recommended for the control of termites and many other sucking, biting and chewing insect pests (Sileshi *et al.*, 2008). However, it is expensive, not readily available and harmful effects to the non - target organisms in the ecosystems (Ahmed, Girma, 2013). In the bid to come up with alternative cheap; readily available; biodegradable and less toxic insecticides, some plant species such as *Jatropha curcas*, *Capsicum spp* and *Azadirachta indica* were discovered to synthesize active secondary metabolites such as phenolic compounds and essential oils with established potent insecticidal activity (Ahmed, Girma, 2013). However, much as such plants have a rich biodiversity in Uganda, very few Ugandans have embraced the use of their extracts in the control of termites (Ssemaganda *et al.*, 2011). This is probably due to the fact that no studies have been carried out to provide relevant and up-to-date information about their termiticidal potency. The aim of this study was to assess the efficacy of crude botanical extracts from *Jatropha curcas* seeds, *Capsicum spp* ripe fruits and *Azadirachta indica* leaves and a synthetic insecticide (imidacloprid) in the control of *Macrotermes spp*.

2 - Materials and Methods

2.1 - Collection of the Botanical Plant Materials

Jatropha curcas seeds, *Azadirachta indica* leaves, *Capsicum spp* ripe fruits were collected from Mukono District and washed with tap water to remove the dust. They were then separately put in different plastic containers as described by (Gitonga *et al.*, 1995). The containers were properly labelled and transported to the Biology Laboratory at the Department of Biological Sciences of Kyambogo University.

2.2 - Drying of the Botanical Plant Materials

In the laboratory, the collected botanical plant materials were separately dried in a cool dry and well ventilated place for a period of one week (7 days) to reduce on their moisture content.

2.3 - Pounding of The botanical Plant Materials

Each category of the botanical plant materials was separately pounded using a mortar and pestle and sieved through a 0.25 mm pore size mesh sieve to obtain uniform fine powdery particles (Salase and Getu, 2009). The powder from each botanical plant material was put in a different plastic container and tightly covered.

2.4 - Preparation of the Varying Concentration Levels of Botanical Extracts

Powder of 5 g, 10 g, 20 g and 30 g from each of the collected botanical plant materials was separately weighed using an analytical weighing balance that measures in grams with an error correction of ± 0.001 . Each weighed quantity of the powder was separately added to 100 ml of distilled water in clean and clearly labelled plastic bottles, stirred thoroughly using a clean stirring rods to evenly distribute the powder in the water so as to obtain four crude botanical extracts with concentration levels of 5%, 10%, 20% and 30% (w/v) for each of the botanical plant material. The bottles were loosely covered with screw caps and left to stand for 48 hours (2 days) in a cool dry place to obtain an infusion. After the two days, the contents in each plastic bottle were

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separately filtered using Whatman number 1 filter paper. The resulting solutions of varying concentration levels were separately kept in clean screw capped plastic bottles at room temperature.

2.5 - Collection of *Macrotermes Spp*

Populations of *Macrotermes spp* (Worker termites) were collected from the mounds in the gardens and bushes around Kyambogo University, Kampala District. The mounds were dug up using a hand hoe and the soil containing the termites put on polyethene sheets. The termite populations were collected from the polyethene sheets using a hair brush and placed in rectangular plastic containers. Dry grass onto which some water had been sprinkled was added to the plastic containers to act as the feed for the termites. The top of each plastic container was covered with a muslin cloth to allow movement of the air in and out of the plastic containers. The containers containing the termites were transported to the Biology laboratory of Kyambogo University and placed in a cool and dark area for 24 hours to simulate the conditions in their galleries.

2.6- Bioassay Procedures for the Varying Concentration Levels of Crude Botanical Extracts

Forty five (45) clean plastic petri dishes were arranged on a clean table. In each petri dish, a clean Whatman number 1 filter paper was placed. For each of the four concentration levels (5%, 10%, 20% and 30%) of the botanical extracts, three (3) filter papers were treated, each with 3 ml. Nine (9) filter papers were treated each with 3 ml of distilled water to act as the control. Using a clean hair brush, five (5) live termites were randomly picked from the plastic containers containing the stock of *Macrotermes spp*. They were placed and kept in each of the petri dishes containing the treated filter papers for 24 hours. All the petri dishes each containing five (5) termites were covered with muslin cloths and randomly arranged in a dark place to simulate the dark environment in the termites' galleries in the mounds. After the 24 hours, the dead termites in each petri dish were counted and recorded in the designed log book.

2.7- Preparation of the Varying Concentration Levels of the Synthetic Insecticide (Imidacloprid)

Imidacloprid at 5%, 10%, 20% and 30% (v/v) concentration levels was prepared. The 5% concentration level (Manufacturer's application rate) was prepared by measuring 5ml of imidacloprid and adding it to 95 ml of distilled water in a plastic beaker and stirred to mix thoroughly. The 10% concentration level was prepared by measuring 10ml of imidacloprid and adding it to 90 ml of distilled water in a plastic beaker and stirred to mix thoroughly. The 20% concentration level was prepared by measuring 20ml of imidacloprid and adding it to 80 ml of distilled water in a plastic beaker and stirred to mix thoroughly. The 30% concentration level was prepared by measuring 30ml of imidacloprid and adding it to 70 ml of distilled water in a plastic beaker and stirred to mix thoroughly.

2.8- Bioassay Procedure for the Varying Concentration Levels of Imidacloprid

Fifteen (15) clean plastic petri dishes were arranged on a clean table. In each petri dish, a Whatman number 1 filter paper was placed. For each of the four concentration levels of imidacloprid, three (3) filter papers were treated each with 3 ml in order to replicate each concentration level three times. Three (3) filter papers were treated each with 3 ml of distilled water to act as the negative control. Using a hair brush, five (5) termites were randomly picked from the plastic containers containing the stock of termites and kept in each of the petri dishes containing the treated filter papers for 24 hours. All the petri dishes each containing five (5) termites were covered with muslin cloths and randomly arranged in a dark place to simulate the dark environment in the termites' galleries in the mounds. After the 24 hours, the dead termites in each petri dish were counted and recorded in the designed log book.

2.9- Calculation of Percentage Mortality

Percentage mortality of the termites due to the treatments was calculated according to the equation below:

Percentage mortality = $\frac{\text{Number of dead termites in the petri dish}}{\text{Total number of termites}} \times 100$

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Total number of termites in the petri dish

2.10- Statistical analysis

The collected data was entered into the Excel spreadsheet and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was carried out with MS Excel Analysis Tool Pack. Means comparisons of treatments were performed at 5% Significance level

3- Results and discussion

Results from the study showed that all the concentration levels of the different botanical extracts and Imidacloprid were able to cause mortality of *Macrotermes spp* (Figure 1, Table 1).

Table 1: Mean Percentage Mortality of *Macrotermes Spp* due to the Varying Concentration Levels of the Botanical Extracts and Imidacloprid

Treatments	Mean Percentage Mortality of <i>Macrotermes Spp</i> due to the Varying Concentration Levels of Botanical Extracts an Imidacloprid			
	5%	10%	20%	30%
<i>Capsicum spp</i>	66.67	86.67	100	100
<i>Jatropha curcas</i>	80	93.33	100	100
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	60	73.33	100	86.67
Imidacloprid	80	100	100	100
Control	0	0	0	0

Figure 1: Mean Percentage Mortality of *Macrotermes Spp* due to the Varying Concentration Levels of the Botanical Extracts and Imidacloprid

Table 2: Results for statistical analysis

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	544.4056	3	181.4685	0.989858	0.430427	3.490295
Within Groups	2199.933	12	183.3278			
Total	2744.339	15				

Results for One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) showed that at p= 5%, F= 0.989858 and Fcrit = 3.490295

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At 5% Concentration Level of the botanical Extracts, *Jatropha curcas* extract caused the highest mean percentage mortality of *Macrotermes spp* (80%) followed by *Capsicum spp* (66.67%) whereas *Azadirachta indica* caused the lowest (60%), at 10% Concentration Level, *Jatropha curcas* extract caused the highest mean percentage mortality of *Macrotermes spp* (93.33%) followed by *Capsicum spp* (86.67%) whereas *Azadirachta indica* caused the lowest (73.33%), at 20% Concentration Level, *Jatropha curcas* and *Capsicum spp* extracts caused the highest mean percentage mortality of *Macrotermes spp* (100%) whereas *Azadirachta indica* caused the lowest (80%), at 30% Concentration Level, both *Jatropha curcas* and *Capsicum spp* extracts caused the highest mean percentage mortality of *Macrotermes spp* (100%) whereas *Azadirachta indica* caused the lowest (86.67%). The mean percentage mortality of *Macrotermes spp* due to 10%, 20% and 30% concentration levels of Imidacloprid was 100% and 80% at 5% concentration level. There was zero mortality of *Macrotermes spp* due to the control (Distilled water).

Jatropha curcas extracts caused mean percentage mortality of termites ranging from 80% at 5% concentration level to 100% at 30% concentration level as compared to the control (Distilled water) that caused no mortality of termites. These results are in agreement with the results got by Yohannes (2006) who recorded 93% to 100% mortality of termites when he used the same concentration levels of crude *J. curcas* seed extracts.

Seeds of *J. curcas* contain oil which oil has been reported as an insecticide due to the presence of several sterols and terpene alcohols that are highly toxic to many insect pests such as termites (Salimon *et al.*, 2012). The toxicity of those components in seed oil of *J. curcas* to insect pests increases with increase in their concentration. This clearly explains why the mean percentage mortality of termites increased with increase in the concentration levels of the *J. curcas* extracts.

It has also been stated that the toxicity of *J. curcas* could be attributed to *Jatrophine* which is the dominant compound in *J. curcas* seeds and it is well known to have contact and stomach poisoning action to the termites (Salimon *et al.*, 2012). High insecticidal performances of *Jatropha curcas* Seed extracts especially at high concentration levels are similar to the report that showed that crude oil extract from the seeds of *J. curcas* have traditionally been used as an insect repellent, molluscicide and rodenticide (Sabiiti, 2002).

Extracts of *Capsicum spp* showed positive effects as insecticide against *Macrotermes spp* of termites especially at high concentration levels of 20% and 30% (Figure 1, Table 1). The toxicity of *Capsicum spp* is majorly attributed to Capsaicinoids though several other toxic compounds are found in the various varieties of *Capsicum spp* (Ahmed and Girma, 2013). Capsaicinoids in *Capsicum spp* kill insects by affecting their physiology (Ahmed and Girma, 2013). It abrades the skin of the insects (roughens the skin or wear it away), causing them to lose water (Salase and Getu, 2009). According to (Ahmed and Girma (2013), the insecticidal activity of Capsaicinoids to insect pests increases with increase in their concentration. This clearly explains why at increasing concentration levels of the *Capsicum spp* extract, high mortality of *Macrotermes spp* of termites was recorded.

Results from the study showed that all the concentration levels of *A. indica* extracts tested were efficacious against *Macrotermes spp* of termites with 20% and 30% concentration levels of the extracts causing the highest termite mortality (Figure 1, Table 1). The toxic property of *Azadirachta indica* is attributed to *Azadirachtin* which is the dominant compound in *A. indica* leaves and seeds (Nisar *et al.*, 2012). *Azadirachtin* acts as contact poison to termites and also has systemic effects when applied on foliage that may be eaten by termites causing their death seeds (Nisar *et al.*, 2012). According to Nisar *et al.* (2012), the toxicity of *Azadirachtin* to insect pests also increases with increase in its concentration. This clearly explains why at increasing concentration levels of the *A. indica*, high mortality of *Macrotermes spp* of termites was recorded. *Azadirachtin* has a broad mode of activity, working as a feeding deterrent, insect growth regulator, and sterilant and may also inhibit oviposition of insect pests (Sabiiti, 2002).

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Although all the concentration levels of the different botanical extracts used in this study were generally efficacious at causing mortality of *Macrotermes spp* of termites, there was difference in the efficacy of the varying concentration levels of these botanical extracts in causing mortality of *Macrotermes spp* of termites in that, higher concentration levels of 20% and 30% generally showed more efficacy in causing mortality of *Macrotermes spp* of termites as compared to the lower concentration levels of 5% and 10%.

Results from the study showed that all the four concentration levels of imidacloprid used were able to cause the mortality of *Macrotermes spp* of termites especially 10%, 20% and 30% which caused 100% mortality (Figure 1, Table 1). Imidacloprid contains chloronicotin, whose mode of action is to interfere with normal nerve impulse transmission by binding to post-synaptic nicotinic acetylcholine receptors of the insect pests which eventually leads to their death. The toxicity of chloronicotin increases with increase in the dose used. This clearly explains why at increasing concentration levels of imidacloprid, high mortality of termites was recorded. The results in this study agree with those obtained by (Zeck, 1992).

Therefore, results from this study indicated that there is no difference in the efficacy of imidacloprid at 10%, 20% and 30% in controlling *Macrotermes spp* of termites because at all those concentration levels, 100% mean percentage mortality of *Macrotermes spp* of termites was recorded (Figure 1, Table 1). However, there was difference in the efficacy 5% concentration level and the rest of the concentration levels in controlling *Macrotermes spp*.

4- Conclusion

Findings from this study showed that all the crude botanical extracts tested against *Macrotermes spp* of termites possess termiticidal potency that could be utilized in the management of *Macrotermes spp* in the fields and households. From the botanical extracts, *Jatropha curcas* and *Capsicum spp* extracts were observed to be the most bio-potent especially at higher concentration levels of 20% and 30%. *Azadirachta indica* extracts also showed some termiticidal properties though the mortality of termites was generally lower than that caused by *Jatropha curcas* and *Capsicum spp* extracts at all concentration levels tested. For the synthetic insecticide (imidacloprid), all the concentration levels tested showed termiticidal properties especially the higher concentration levels of 10%, 20% and 30% whereas 5% caused relatively lower mortality of *Macrotermes spp* as compared to the other concentration levels. At $p = 5\%$, $F = 0.989858$ and $F_{crit} = 3.490295$ hence there was no significant difference in the in-vitro efficacy of the botanical extracts and imidacloprid in controlling termites.

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